

ISic3326

I.Sicily inscription 3326

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

base

or altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2013.10.04

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Florida

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. numini
2. praesen
3. tissimo
4. [A]esculapio
5. [R]oscius Ae
6. [li]anus Salviu[s]
7. u(t) v(overat) r(estituta) s(alute)
8. [li]bens d(onum) d(edit)
9. Nonis Mart(iis)
10. [Al]bino et M[aximo]
11. co(n)[ss(ulibus)]

Apparatus

Text of 1996, 796

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175829

EDR 073896

EDCS 13900430

Bibliography

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